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HEALTH HUMAN CAPITAL AND LIFE EXPECTANCY IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN (SSA) COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This paper investigates the effects of health human capital on life expectancy at birth. The analysis was conducted on 42 Sub-Saharan African countries using panel data from 2000 to 2020 obtained from World Bank Development indicators. We employed the Pooled Ordinary Least Square regression technique, the Random and Fixed Effect models to investigate the relationship between the variables. Relying on the Fixed Effect estimates based on the Hausman test, results revealed a positive significant relationship between health human capital and life expectancy. However, being a non-linear relationship, the effect of health human capital on life expectancy was initially negative and then turned positive significantly. A major policy recommendation is that SSA countries should make substantial increases in health human capital to improve life expectancy of the population in the region.

KEYWORDS: Fixed Effect, Health Human Capital, Life Expectancy, Sub-Sahara Africa

1-Introduction

Life expectancy at birth is one of the most widely used measures of health outcomes in the world today. It serves as a fundamental gauge of a population's wellbeing and healthcare strength. The life expectancy of a country is influenced by a variety of factors, including its social, environmental, and economic climate, public health, and the healthcare system (Ho & Hendi, 2018). One of the main goals of every nation in the world is to increase life expectancy; therefore every country is working hard to lower mortality and enhance their citizens' health status and conditions (Rahman, 2022). This objective is pursued through various means, such as implementing comprehensive healthcare systems, promoting healthy lifestyles and advancing medical research and technology. Additionally, governments often prioritize initiatives aimed at reducing the prevalence of diseases, enhancing access to quality healthcare services and ensuring adequate nutrition for their populations (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2021).

WHO (2023) defines life expectancy at birth as the average number of years that a newborn could expect to live, if he or she were to pass through life exposed to the sex- and age-specific death rates prevailing at the time of his or her birth, for a specific year,

in a given country, territory, or geographic area. However, understanding the determinants of life expectancy at birth has become a very important issue for developing countries on several grounds. Life expectancy assumes a vital role not only in case of human health but also under the context of national development. Improving life expectancy is among the major prerogatives for countries seeking to improve the health status of their citizens, and therefore they all are trying to decrease mortality and improve their health status and conditions (Uddin et al., 2023). For instance, Shahbaz et al. (2019) postulate that better life expectancy at birth is the most essential factor that affects peoples' health and this permits workers to maintain their productivity, thus increasing economic growth. Additionally, the need for longer life expectancy tends to increase the scale of the health care industries in emerging nations (Ha & Nam, 2022), both at the local and macro levels.

According to the WHO, the average life expectancy at birth in SSA was 61 years in 2019. This is an improvement from previous years, as the average life expectancy in SSA was 55 years in 2000. However, there are significant variations in life expectancy among different countries in SSA. For example, the countries with the highest life expectancy in SSA were Mauritius (74 years), Seychelles (73 years), and Cape Verde (72 years). On the other hand, the countries with the lowest life expectancy in SSA were Chad (54 years), Central Africa Republic (53 years) and Sierra Leone (52 years). These disparities in life expectancy among different countries in SSA highlight the significant health inequalities that exist across the region (Audain et al., 2017). Efforts to improve healthcare infrastructure, increase access to education and economic opportunities, and address specific health challenges are crucial in reducing these disparities and improving overall health outcomes in the region.

Health human capital can be thought of as an investment in a human being that is essential to preserving their health and capability (Patton et al., 2016). Fogel (1994) contend that health human capital may possibly be seen as a technological improvement, where the level of health human capital is a share of the factor productivity. According to Wright and McMahan, (2011) health human capital refers to the knowledge, skills and abilities related to health care that individuals acquire through education, training and experience. One of the key concepts in the literature of health human capital is the idea of health human capital investment. This concept highlights the value of investing in education and training as a means of increasing productivity, improving health care service delivery, and ultimately improving overall health outcomes. Research has shown that a highly skilled and knowledgeable healthcare workforce can lead to better health outcomes, reduced morbidity and increased longevity. The low level of health human capital can be accounted for the prevalence of HIV/AIDS in SSA region (Breinholt and Nielsen).

Investment in health human capital is a major contributor to a person's overall wellbeing, and can be consumed for pleasure or invested for gain. When consumed, health capital provides a person with pleasure and joy but when invested, it can yield a significant

return in the form of increased productivity and income (Tengiz & Dangadze, 2018). According to Grossman (1972), health capital is becoming increasingly important as the consumption of other goods and services in modern day. By investing in health human capital, not only can we increase the number of able-bodied people in the population, but also reduce the rate of sickness and mortality. These investments can take various forms such as education, nutrition, access to healthcare and environmental factors (Sørensen, 2018).

Investing in healthcare and health human capital can have a significant impact on life expectancy in SSA (Bloom & Canning, 2003). According to the World Bank, the life expectancy at birth was 61 years in 2019. This is an improvement from previous years, but still lower than the global average of 72 years (Nketiah-Amponsah, 2019). Investments in health human capital can help the poor achieve inclusive growth and a living environment through social security measures, which may help inverse the effects of diseases and keep other susceptible groups from experiencing extreme poverty which in turn has a positive impact on life expectancy (Wang et al., 2021).

Similarly, the World Bank's report in 2021 found out that investing in health human capital can significantly improve life expectancy. The report estimated that increasing health spending by 1% of GDP could increase life expectancy by 0.4-1.2 years, depending on the level of initial health spending. Current growths in the use of the health service as well as the unit costs indicate that these pressures are likely to persist. However, there are clear benefits to investing in health; an OECD research by James (2017) found out that a 10% increase in health spending was associated with a gain of 3.5 months of life expectancy across the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development from 1995 to 2015. The low level of health human capital can be accounted for the prevalence of HIV/AIDS in SSA region.

Many studies have shown that there exist a positive relationship between health human capital and life expectancy but that this relationship is much stronger in countries with good quality of institutions (Kalemli-Ozcan et al., 2015). Furthermore, it has been found out that healthcare spending can have a significant impact on health outcome and economic growth. A study by the WHO found out that every \$1 spent on healthcare could result in a return of \$2-4 to the economy (WHO, 2017). This is so because healthier individuals are more productive and less likely to miss work due to illness. Additionally, investing in health human capital can lead to the development of new technologies and treatments, which can create jobs and stimulate innovation in related industries (Sima et al., 2020). However, it is important to note that simply increasing healthcare spending does not guarantee better health outcomes or economic growth. The quality and efficiency of healthcare delivery are also crucial factors (Widayati & Adriani, 2017). Therefore, policymakers must carefully consider how healthcare resources are allocated and ensure that they are being used effectively to improve both health outcomes and economic performance.

One of the best routes to providing better care for a health system is to focus on increasing its health outlays on health capital and preventive measures as the economy expands. Yet despite the global increases in health expenditures, the WHO has realised that investment in health human capital has generally received less attention in government budgets in the developing regions of the world, especially those in SSA, where incomes are low and resources are relatively scarce (WHO, 2010). Consequently, expenditures on health human capital in SSA constitute only a small proportion of GDP compared to the situation found in more developed economies. In 2010 for example, health expenditures constituted only about 6 percent of GDP in SSA, while such outlays constituted as much as 13 to 17 percent of GDP in the OECD nations and in North America, respectively (WHO, 2010). This lack of funding has resulted in a number of challenges for healthcare systems in SSA. Access to healthcare is limited, with many people unable to afford basic treatments or even access to healthcare facilities. This has led to high rates of preventable diseases and mortality, particularly among children and women. Additionally, the quality of care is often subpar due to inadequate resources and staffing levels. Healthcare workers are overburdened and underpaid, leading to high turnover rates and shortages in critical areas such as nursing and primary care.

This work will make it possible for this region to identify the extent to which each of the factors identified can influence life expectancy and what areas to improve upon in order to make life expectancy better within the SSA region. The findings of this study would help inform policy makers on the need for conscious efforts to dedicate considerable amount of resources to healthcare which will also facilitate the achievement of the targets of the sustainable millennium goal. This will go further to improve life expectancy. More so, the recommendations will help to inform government on the basic aspects of life that need to be improved on in order that its citizens enjoy longer life expectancy such as improving their level of education, hygiene and sanitation, improving nutritional status as well as level of income.

The rest of the paper proceeds as follows: in section 2 we explore existing empirical works on the relationship between health human capital and life expectancy and bring out the research gap. This is followed by section 3 which comprises of the methodology where we explore the method of data analysis, sources of data, empirical techniques as well as specifying the model. Section four contains presentation and discussion of results while section five embodies the conclusions. Section 6 is the acknowledgements and Section seven is references.

2- Review of Related Studies

Health Human Capital and Life Expectancy

Health human capital refers to the accumulation of knowledge, skills and experiences that contribute to the maintenance of an individual's health and overall well-being. The importance of health human capital has been extensively studied in the field of economics to determine its impact on life expectancy. Recent empirical works have demonstrated a

positive correlation between health human capital and life expectancy, providing evidence for the importance of investing in health education and healthcare services. Much empirical work has been done on the relationship between life expectancy and its determinants. Despite the variety of literature exploring the nexus between health expenditure and health outcome, the debate is still ongoing.

One study conducted by Wang et al. (2021) examined the association between health human capital and life expectancy in China. The researchers found out that the level of education, healthcare utilization and health awareness were all significant predictors of life expectancy. In particular, individuals with higher educational attainment were found to have a longer life expectancy, likely due to their increased access to health information and resources. This study highlights the importance of promoting health education and rising health awareness to improve overall health outcomes.

Another study by Gillum et al. (2020) analysed the relationship between healthcare expenditures and life expectancy in countries around the world. The researchers found out that countries with higher healthcare expenditures had longer life expectancies, indicating that investing in health care services can have a significant impact on population health. This study also demonstrated that the effect of healthcare expenditure on life expectancy was significantly greater in low and middle-income countries, underscoring the importance of directing resources towards these regions.

In the same vein, another study on 36 OECD countries from 1999 to 2018 on determinants of life expectancy at birth by Roffia et al. (2023) endorses the importance of healthcare expenditures and health care system in influencing life expectancy. They made use of cross-country fixed-effects multiple regression analysis with year and country dummies and used dynamic models, backward stepwise selection, and Arellano–Bond estimators. The results revealed that per capita health-care expenditure, out-of-pocket expenditure, physician density, hospital bed density, social spending, GDP level, participation ratio to labour, prevalence of chronic respiratory diseases, temperature and total size of the population have an influence on life expectancy at birth.

The conclusion of investigations done on many countries (regions) tends to be in harmony with those carried out in single countries. For instance, Nkemga et al. (2021) in their study investigated two main objectives: the first was to evaluate and compare the impact of public and private health spending on life expectancy, and secondly to examine the causal link among public health expenditure, private health expenditure and life expectancy in Cameroon. Applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique on annual data from 1980 to 2014, they found out that private health expenditure has a positive and significant impact on life expectancy while public health expenditure has no significant impact on life expectancy in Cameroon.

Nketiah-Amponsah (2019) in a recent study also confirms the positive association between health care spending and life expectancy. He investigated the impact of health expenditures on health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa and discovered, above all, that health expenditure is less income elastic. His findings revealed that health expenditure

exerts a positive and significant impact on under-five mortality, maternal mortality and life expectancy. Specifically, the results proved that a 1% increase in health expenditure per capita resulted in a 0.5 percent reduction in under-five mortality and a 0.35 % fall in maternal mortality, while improving life expectancy by 0.06%.

Sango-Coker and Bein (2018), researched on the impact of healthcare spending on life expectancy in selected West African Countries. Data was obtained from World Bank Indicators within the period of 16 years (from 1999 - 2014). Using pooled regression and pairwise correlation techniques of analyses, the results showed that empirical female population lived longer than the male population and a positive relationship was obtained between the variables of healthcare spending and life expectancy for the public healthcare sector. The results also revealed a negative relationship between these variables for the private healthcare sector. It was therefore recommended that the government, policy and decision-makers should focus on increasing the expenditure on the public healthcare system to achieve positive outcomes for increased life expectancy against other healthcare sectors that remain expensive and inaccessible to the population. Makuta and O'Hare (2015) examined the relationship between public spending on health and quality of governance in 43 Sub-Saharan African countries. Using data for the period 1996-2011 and employing the two-stage least squares regression technique, they found out that good governance improves the positive impact of public spending on health and such impact is larger in those countries where the quality of governance is higher. It denotes that an increase in public spending reduces infant mortality and increases life expectancy sharply as compared to other countries having poor quality of governance.

In another study, Dianda and Ouedraogo (2021) examined the synergistic effect of government health spending and institutional quality on health capital accumulation in WAEMU countries over the period 2000-2015. Using annual data from eight countries in WAEMU, they developed four equations and followed the macroeconomic health production function developed by Fayissa and Gutema (2005) based on Grossman's model (1972). Using the two stage least squares technique, they discovered that public health spending and institutional quality have a positive effect on accumulation of health capital and the variables also have a combined effect on the dependent variable. They came to a conclusion that to gain maximum returns from government health spending, institutional quality must be improved.

Beyond health human capital (healthcare expenditures), socio-economic factors such as inflation, education, income (GDP per capita), institutional quality, and urban population also play a critical role in determining life expectancy. For instance, a study by Chetty et al. (2016) demonstrated that the life expectancy gap between the richest and poorest Americans had widened over the past few decades, suggesting that socioeconomic disparities have significant effects on health outcomes.

Further away from healthcare expenditures, the quality of healthcare services also plays a critical role of social determinants of health in shaping life expectancy. A study by Jia et

al. (2019) investigated the relationship between quality of care and life expectancy among older adults in rural China. The researcher found out that individuals who received better quality care had significantly longer life expectancy than those who did not. The study highlights the importance of ensuring that healthcare services are accessible, affordable and of high quality to maximize their impact on population health.

Furthermore, recent research has highlighted the crucial role of environmental factors such as carbon emission, pollution and access to water in shaping life expectancy. Uddin et al. (2023) revisited the socioeconomic factors determining life expectancy in selected Asian countries from 2002 to 2020 by focusing on the role of institutional quality, financial development and environmental degradation proxied by carbon emissions and ecological footprint. They employed CIPS (Cross-Sectional Im, Pesaran, and Shin) unit root tests, CS-ARDL (Cross-Sectional Augmented Distributed Lag (CS-ARDL), FMOLS (Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares), and DOLS (Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares) for the empirical examination of the data. Their long-run estimates reveal that institutional quality, financial development, and health expenditure variables contribute to longer life expectancy, while carbon emissions, ecological footprint, birth rate, mortality rate and population growth reduce life expectancy in the selected Asian countries. Based on these findings, they recommend strengthening of the financial sector, increase in healthcare budget allocation, the adoption of clean and green technology and stringent environmental pollution regulatory policies in order to improving life expectancy and overall human well-being and achieving the ultimate goals of sustainable development. Despite the consensus in literature on the positive relationship between healthcare expenditure and life expectancy, other studies still found a negative relationship between healthcare expenditures and life expectancy. Nagarajah et al. (2018) carried out a study on the determinant of Life Expectancy in Malaysia. Using data collected annually from World Bank database and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method for their investigations, they found out that urbanization exposes Malaysians to better health care and consequently better life expectancy, yet health expenditure has negatively influenced life expectancy in Malaysia. Gupta et al. (1999) also found a negative significant effect of urbanization on health outcome.

Further, a study by Renolds and Avendano (2018) found that the United States, which has the highest healthcare expenditure per capita in the world, had one of the lowest life expectancies among high-income countries, suggesting a negative effect of healthcare expenditure on life expectancy. The authors noted that factors such as social inequality, unhealthy behaviours and environmental pollution may contribute to this trend.

Recent empirical studies provide significant evidence of the importance of health human capital in improving life expectancy. Healthcare expenditure, education, socio-economic and environmental determinants of health outcome all play a crucial role in promoting population health. Therefore, policy makers and healthcare providers should prioritise investing in health education, improving access to healthcare services, and addressing socioeconomic disparities to promote better health outcomes for all.

Most previous studies have focused on the life expectancy and its determinants while a few also pay attention to human capital and life expectancy. Existing literature on health human capital such as the work of Breinholt and Nielsen, (2005) focused on its relationship with economic growth. That notwithstanding, there is almost no empirical work that has focused on the relationship between health human capital and life expectancy in SSA thereby leaving a huge gap in literature which this study aims to bridge with its findings.

3- Methodology

3.1 Data and Description of Variables

This study aims to investigate the effect of health human capital on life expectancy at birth in SSA. To achieve this goal, data is collected for 42 out of the 48 SSA countries covering a period of 21 years. Data on all variables is collected from the World Bank development indicators from 2000 to 2020. The countries are selected based on data availability for the countries for some of the most important independent variables over the stipulated period of investigation. The countries included in the estimations are Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Democratic Republic of Congo, Republic of Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Djibouti, Equatorial Guinea, Ethiopia, The Gambia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Libya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

The dependent variable used in this study is life expectancy at birth measured in years. The main independent variable is health human capital proxied by healthcare expenditure. Other control variables included in the study include access to water (H2O) which is a percentage of the population using safe water services, GDP per capita measured in purchasing power parity, inflation which is annual inflation rate, carbon emission measured in metric ton per capita, degree of urbanization which takes the percentage of the population dwelling in urban areas, the prevalence of HIV which is the percentage of the population infected by HIV/AIDS and institutional quality which is an index of governance indicators computed using the principal component analysis. These variables were selected based on empirical and theoretical backing.

3.2 Model Specification

In order to investigate the effect of health human capital on life expectancy at birth, which is the objective of this study, we specified a model where life expectancy at birth is the main dependent variable and the independent variable is Health Human Capital (HHC) proxied by health care expenditure.

We specify the model based on Grossman's (1972) model on health production function which expresses health outcome as a function of a vector of health inputs. There is a well-established relationship between health human capital and life expectancy. Countries that spend more on healthcare tend to have higher life expectancy than those that spend less, everything being equal. The model is specified following the specification used by many

other authors (Uddin et al., 2023; Radmehr & Adebayo, 2022; Azam & Awan, 2022; Mahalik et al., 2022). The model is stated in the following functional form as:

$$Y=f(X) \dots\dots\dots(3.1)$$

In order to investigate the effect of health human capital on life expectancy at birth, which is our objective, we specified a model where life expectancy at birth is the main dependent variable while the independent variable is health care expenditure as a proxy for health human capital (HHC).

To Determine the Effect of Health Human capital on Life Expectancy at Birth in Sub-Saharan Africa

$$LEB = f (HHC, GDPca, H_2O, Inflation, CO_2, URB, HIV, Ggov) \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

LEB= Life expectancy at birth in years

HHC= health human capital (current healthcare expenditure per capita)

H₂O= % of population using safely managed drinking water services

GDPca= per capita income (Per capita GDP in purchasing power parity (PPP) US in dollar)

Inflation = inflation, CPI (annual percentage)

CO₂ = carbon dioxide emission (metric ton per capita)

URB= degree of urbanization (% of total population in urban areas)

HIV= Prevalence of HIV (% of total population)

Ggov= institutional quality index (computed using principal component analysis)

Following panel data model specification, the above equation can then be stated in the following the standard panel data formulation (3.2) as seen below:

$$LEB_{it} = \beta_0 + HHC_{it} + Xn_{it} + \mu_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

Where: LEB_{it} denotes life expectancy at birth, HHC_{it} represent the main independent variable, Xn_{it} represents control variables over the time period; μ_{it} is country-specific effects; and it ϵ represents the error term. The complete model showing the relationship between health care expenditure and life expectancy at birth is presented below:

$$LEB_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln HHC_{it} + \beta_2 \ln GDPca_{it} + \beta_3 H_2O_{it} + \beta_4 \ln INF_{it} + \beta_5 \ln CO_2_{it} + \beta_6 URB_{it} + \beta_7 HIV_{it} + \beta_8 Ggov_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(3.4)$$

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_6, \beta_8 > 0$ while $\beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_7 < 0$

β_0 = the intercept

β_1 to β_8 = coefficients of the independent variables (unknown parameter) slopes such that,

ϵ = error term.

3.3 Diagnostic Evaluation Techniques

3.3.1 Cross Sectional Dependence

Cross sectional dependence is basically one of the first steps in estimating panel data model and it helps direct the use of subsequent tests. Panel data can be subject to pervasive cross-sectional dependence, whereby all units in the same cross-section are

correlated. This is usually attributed to the effect of some unobserved common factors, common to all units and affecting each of them, although possibly in different ways (Henningsen & Henningsen, 2019). The test for cross-sectional dependence (CSD) is to test whether the residuals are correlated across entities. If the null hypothesis of no cross-sectional dependence is rejected, then there is evidence of cross-sectional dependence in the model.

The null hypothesis is “there is no correlation of the residual”

Pesaran (2004) has proposed the following formula for balanced panel:

$$CD = \sqrt{2T/N(N-1) \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij}}$$

For unbalanced panel:

$$CD = \sqrt{2T/N(N-1) \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \sqrt{T_{ij} \hat{\rho}_{ij}}}$$

3.3.2 Panel Unit Root

We proceed by using the IPS and the Fisher augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test to verify the stationarity of variables. The Im - Pesaran - Shin (IPS) and Fisher ADF panel unit root test is used in this study to ascertain if the variables are stationary at level or after differencing them. Im, Pesaran and Shin (1997) suggest a procedure for testing stationarity for panel data which uses a standardized t-bar test statistic based on the Augmented Dickey Fuller test statistics averaged across panels. The t-bar is obtained from an average of the individual ADF statistics that is from running ADF test on each individual time series. The IPS and Fisher ADF unit root test the following hypotheses

H0: All panels contain unit roots (all panels are non-stationary)

H1: Some panels do not contain unit roots (some panels are stationary). To check for unit root in heterogeneous panel the test is based on the ADF. The overall test statistics is based on the arithmetic mean of individual series, a series may be represented by ADF as Ashghar et al. (2015) present it:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \bar{w}_i + \rho y_{i,t-1} \sum_{j=1}^{p_i} \rho_{ij} \Delta p y_{i,t-j} + v_{i,t}$$

IPS unit root test model is written as

$$\bar{t}_r = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N t_{it}(p_i) \text{ where } p_i \text{ is the lag order}$$

ADF test

$$A_i = \frac{\sqrt{N(T)}[\bar{t}_r - E(t_r)]}{\sqrt{\text{var } t_r}} \dots$$

An important feature of IPS is that it permits cross sectional units to vary across groups under the alternative hypothesis which implies that they do not converge towards equilibrium value at the same speed as opposed to the Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) test which is more even though they have the same null hypothesis. By allowing some panels to be non-stationary, the IPS test is more suitable for the present study.

3.4 Econometric Strategies

3.4.1 The Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS)

The POLS technique by Henri Theil (1953) is a statistical technique used to estimate the parameters of a linear regression model for panel data. POLS is an effective tool when we want to estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables, assuming that the relationships are constant across all entities. By pooling the data from different entities, POLS regression allows for the estimation of common coefficient for the independent variables assuming that the relationships are constant across all entities. This can provide more efficiency and statistical power compared to separate time series or cross-sectional analyses as applied in this work.

POLS is most suitable when the time is smaller than the number of panels. It can produce unbiased estimate even in the presence of heteroscedasticity. When considering using POLS, there are some commonly employed pre and post-regression tests to consider such as test of stationarity and other diagnostic tests such as autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity as well as robustness checks and residual analysis.

A major limitation of POLS regression is related to potential heterogeneity across individuals or time period. The Fixed and Random effects can be used where there is significant variation in the relationships between dependent and independent variables across entity.

3.4.2 Fixed and Random Effect

Fixed effects regression method controls for omitted variables in panel data when the omitted variables are time-invariant but country-variant. Thus fixed effect method controls for omitted variables that varies across countries but do not change over time, for instance, institutional quality, cultural, historical and geographical differences. The fixed effect regression method has n different intercepts for each country which is represented by binary variable to absorb the influence of all omitted variables that are country-specific and time invariant. The introduction of country-specific time-invariant variable would produce fixed effects regression model as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_1 x_{it} + \alpha_i + \mu_{it}$$

Where $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_2 z_i$, z_i = unobserved country-specific time-invariant variable and α is the entity-fixed effects and its variations come from omitted variables z_i .

The presence of unobserved country-specific and time-invariant variables causes endogeneity problem and biases the estimated coefficients hence the FE method seeks to resolve the problem through the process of “entity demeaned” OLS algorithm. The process uses two steps to address the endogeneity problem by subtracting average of country-specific effect from each variable after which the regression is estimated using the entity demeaned variables. Taking the average of country-specific effects ($\bar{Y}_i = \beta_1 \bar{X}_i + \alpha_i + \bar{\mu}_i$) from both sides of equation of ($Y_{it} = \beta_1 x_{it} + \alpha_i + \mu_{it}$) gives us:

$$\tilde{y}_{it} = \beta_1 \tilde{x}_{it} + \tilde{\mu}_{it}$$

Where, \tilde{y}_{it} , \tilde{x}_{it} are the country-demeaned variables that are used in fixed effects estimation

NB: $\bar{Y} = 1/T \sum Y_{it} \quad T=1, \bar{X}$ and $\bar{\mu}$ are similarly defined.

The process hence eliminates the country-specific effect from the model and the mean value of the error term ($\bar{\mu}_i$) remain the same as the actual value of the country-specific error terms (μ_i) since the error term does not change over time. The FE model estimation technique assumes heterogeneity in the error term across countries and hence suitable to deal with heteroscedasticity in panel regression estimation. Unlike pooled OLS estimation technique, fixed effect estimation addresses the omitted variable bias by controlling for fixed effects but has the tendency of compounding the problem of measurement error (Hauk & Wacziarg, 2009).

Random Effects model on the other hand assumes that there is no correlation between unobserved country-specific time-invariant effects and explanatory variables. Thus $Cov(\mu_{it}, x_{it}) = 0$. The model postulates that although country-specific time-invariant and the explanatory variables are uncorrelated, influence of such unobserved variables must be specified into the regression model. RE model therefore uses all available data, produces unbiased parameter estimate and smallest standard error, but the unobserved country-specific time-invariant variable would produce omitted variable bias.

4- Presentation of Results and Discussions

4.1 General Description of Variables

The data used for this analysis is extracted from the WDI for 42 SSA countries for a period of 21years spanning from 2000 to 2020. This section presents the summary statistics for the life expectancy at birth for the selected 42 countries and healthcare expenditures and other control variables. This is seen on the table below.

Table 4.1 Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Life Expectancy at Birth (LEB)	881	58.85423	7.444169	41.957	84.46585
Health Human Capital (HHC)	863	180.8858	212.0319	6.717034	1443.169
Access to water (H2O)	877	62.11636	16.61987	18.08545	99.89152
GDP per capita (GDPpca)	882	2036.948	2942.808	111.9272	22942.61
Inflation	841	9.729344	34.88048	-9.797647	557.2018
Carbon Emission (CO2)	840	18799.51	62656.24	1.671	447927.2
Degree of Urbanisation (URB)	882	41.62754	18.10227	8.036	90.092
Prevalence of HIV (HIV)	861	4.82288	5.983487	.1	25.9

Institutional quality (Ggov)	838	-1.609356	1.424478	-4.601207	2.187788
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Source: Author's compilation

From the table above, the average total health care expenditure per capita for SSA stands at US\$180.886 while the average life expectancy at birth is 58.85 years. The minimum life expectancy at birth in this region is 41.96years while the highest life expectancy stands at 84.4years which shows a wide gap in longevity among SSA countries. Statistics also show that majority of the population in SSA countries have access to at least safely managed water services (an average of about 62%). The mean GDPpca for this region is US\$2036.94 while inflation rate stands at 9.7% on average. More to that, the statistics show that 41.6% of the population of this region dwells in urban areas while the majority of the population resides in rural areas. This implies that the degree of urbanization in SSA is still very low with some countries still having less than 10% of the population residing in urban areas as seen in the minimum value of 8.036%.

HIV prevalence is also high in the region with some countries having up to about 25.9% prevalence rate which partly explains high mortality rate in the region leading to low life expectancy. The mean value for institutional quality is -0.652 which is an indication that institutions in SSA are weak and this can have an effect on the effectiveness of health care expenditures on health outcomes. The mean value for carbon dioxide emission is 18799.511kt which shows that the level of pollution of the environment by fossil fuel is high and this can cause many diseases leading death hence low life expectancy.

4.2 Cross-Sectional Dependency

The CD test is conducted under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence. P-values less than 0.05 and close to zero indicate presence of cross-section dependence, thereby necessitating the use of second generation unit root tests to ascertain the level of stationarity of the modeled variables. Among the existing second generation unit root tests, we employed the Pesaran's CADF panel unit root test proposed by Pesaran (2003).

Table 4.2 Results of Pesaran CD test for Cross Sectional Dependence

Variable	CD test	P-value
Life expectancy at birth (LEB)	126.356	0.000
Health human capital (LHHC)	66.891	0.000
LHHC_Sq	85.492	0.000
Access to water (H ₂ O)	109.316	0.000
GDP per Capita (LGDPpca)	109.316	0.000
Inflation	19.143	0.000
Carbon emission (LCO ₂)	83.644	0.000
Degree of urbanization (URB)	104.52	0.000
Prevalence (HIV)	42.21	0.000
Institutional Quality (Ggov)	.529	0.597

Authors Compilation

Based on the results of the Pesaran's CD test, there are indications that the non-existence of cross-sectional dependence in the errors occurs only with the governance variables while the rest of the variables pronounce cross sectional dependence. Thus, first generation Panel Unit Root test is done for Governance and second generation test for the others.

4.3 Panel Unit Root Tests Estimates

Table 4.3 First Generation Unit Root Test

Variables	IPS		Fisher ADF		Remark
	t-statistics	P-value	t-statistics	P-value	
Institutional Quality (Ggov)	-1.7708	0.0797	-3.2031	0.0008	I(0)

Author's compilation Notes: IPS= Im, Pesaran and Shin; I(0)=stationary at levels, I(2) stationary after second difference.

Table 4.4 Second Generation Unit Root test

Variable	CADF Test		
	t-statistic	P-value	Remark
Life expectancy at birth (LEB)	-2.086	0.019	I(0)
Health human capital (LHHC)	-1.781	0.037	I(0)
LHHC_Sq	-1.781	0.037	I(0)
Access to water (H ₂ O)	-10.782	0.000	I(2)
GDP per Capita (LGDPpca)	-2.441	0.000	I(0)
Inflation	-10.143	0.000	I(0)
Carbon emission (LCO ₂)	-2.323	0.000	I(0)
Degree of urbanization (URB)	-3.031	0.000	I(2)
Prevalence of HIV (HIV)	-2.094	0.014	I(0)

Author's compilation Notes: I(0)=stationary at levels, I(2) stationary after second difference.

The result of the tests for unit roots is reported on table 4.3 with a null hypothesis that the variables have no unit-roots. The IPS test for unit root and the fisher test were employed as first generation unit test to ascertain the stationarity property of institutional quality while the presence of cross sectional dependence necessitated the employment of a second generation unit test for the other independent variables.

The CADF test for unit root by Pesaran was employed to test for stationarity in the model. The results revealed that the degree or urbanization (URB) and access to water (H₂O) were stationary only after second difference while all the other variables were stationary at levels. To enhance the statistical power of the model the pooled OLS is conducted.

4.4 Testing for Multicollinearity

Table 4.4 Presentation of Pairwise correlation results

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) LEB	1.000									
(2) LHHC	0.423	1.000								
(3) LHHC_sq	0.423	1.000	1.000							
(4) H20	0.407	0.643	0.643	1.000						
(5) LGDPpca	0.398	0.807	0.807	0.704	1.000					
(6) inflation	-0.061	-0.133	-0.133	-0.153	-0.110	1.000				
(7) LCO2	0.218	0.260	0.260	0.198	0.519	0.053	1.000			
(8) URB	0.295	0.496	0.496	0.635	0.724	-0.055	0.323	1.000		
(9) HIV	-0.321	0.284	0.284	0.243	0.239	-0.003	0.087	0.005	1.000	
(10) Ggov	0.015	0.309	0.309	0.422	0.272	.151	0.019	0.014	0.435	1.000

Author's compilation

From the above table, Multicollinearity is detected mostly between health human capital and its quadratic term at 1, and between aggregate institutional quality indicators and individual institutional quality indicators. Multicollinearity is said to constitute a problem if the correlation coefficient exceeds 0.8 (Das, 2019). As a solution to the problem, Das (2019) suggests that multicollinearity can amongst other ways be reduced by centering the collinear variable. Alternatively, transforming the variable by differencing can also provide a solution. We resorted to differencing health human capital to solve the problem of correlation between it and the squared term and multicollinearity was no longer an issue among the explanatory variables.

Table 4.5: Matrix of Correlation after correcting for Multicollinearity

LEB	D.LHHC	LHHC_sq	H20	LGDPpca	inflation	LCO2	URB	HIV
LEB	1.0000							
LHHC								
D1.	-0.0770	1.0000						
LHHC_sq	0.4073	-0.0046	1.0000					
H20	0.3935	-0.0807	0.6357	1.0000				
LGDPpca	0.3768	-0.0866	0.8068	0.6972	1.0000			
Inflation	-0.0132	-0.0951	-0.0880	-0.1395	-0.1093	1.0000		
LCO2	0.2168	-0.0631	0.2591	0.1961	0.5202	0.0619	1.0000	
URB	0.2782	-0.1050	0.4833	0.6328	0.7177	-0.0752	0.3140	1.0000
HIV	-0.3184	0.0145	0.2968	0.2503	0.2504	0.0147	0.0886	0.0108
Ggov	0.0037	0.0392	0.3110	0.4192	0.2722	-0.1284	0.0199	0.0063

Authors' compilation

After differencing health human capital, the problem of collinearity is reduced at first difference. The results reveal that health human capital has a negative relationship with LEB but after a given threshold, an increase in health human capital tends to have a positive relationship with LEB as indicated by the positive coefficient of its quadratic term (HHC_sq). The results also portray that there is a negative relationship between inflation and life expectancy at birth as well as between prevalence of HIV and LEB such that 1% increase in inflation and HIV will decrease life expectancy at birth by 0.0132% and 0.3184% respectively which is in line with a priori expectations. This also aligns with the work of Panahi and Aleemran, (2016) which found a negative relationship between inflation and LEB.

4.5 Pooled Ordinary Least Squares Regression (POLs), Fixed Effect (FE) and Random Effect (RE)

The results relating to the effect of health human capital on life expectancy using the POLs, random and fixed effect is presented on Table 4.6 below. Based on the Hausman test, the fixed effect model is appropriate for estimating this model. Furthermore, no endogeneity is assumed. Also, the data is tested for heteroskedasticity and serial correlation, but no evidence found.

The pooled OLS results generally show a significant result with majority of the relationships being significant at 1%. Model 1 shows the relationship between HHC life expectancy with the individual effect of the components of institutional quality while model 2 shows their combined effect using the governance index composed using the principal component analysis. The results reveal a positive significant relationship between access to water, HHC_sq, carbon emission and life expectancy at birth while degree of urbanization, and HIV have significant but negative relationship with LEB an indication that LEB at birth decreases by their coefficients as they increase by 1%.

Table 4.6: Pooled Ordinary Least Squares Regression (POLs), Fixed Effect (FE) and Random Effect (RE)

VARIABLES	Independent Variable: Life Expectancy at Birth					
	Pooled OLS		Fixed Effect		Random Effect	
	Model (1)	Model (2)	Model (1)	Model (2)	Model (1)	Model (2)
D.LHHC		-2.158	-2.277***	-2.335***	-2.277***	-2.358***
		(1.353)	(0.485)	(0.450)	(0.485)	(0.489)
LHHC_sq	1.553***	1.492***	1.320***	1.344***	1.320***	1.378***
	(0.214)	(0.207)	(0.146)	(0.139)	(0.146)	(0.148)
H2O	0.177***	0.144***	0.102***	0.059***	0.102***	0.108***
	(0.020)	(0.021)	(0.020)	(0.020)	(0.020)	(0.020)
LGDPpca	0.310	-0.574	1.062***	0.677***	1.062***	0.894***
	(0.484)	(0.477)	(0.265)	(0.260)	(0.265)	(0.278)
Inflation	0.008	0.015	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002
	(0.008)	(0.010)	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.004)	(0.004)
LCO2	0.554***	0.998***	0.823***	0.888***	0.823***	0.846***

	(0.144)	(0.154)	(0.163)	(0.161)	(0.163)	(0.166)
URB	-0.084***	-0.052***	0.298***	0.480***	0.298***	0.301***
	(0.018)	(0.019)	(0.031)	(0.033)	(0.031)	(0.031)
HIV	-0.643***	-0.647***	-0.872***	-0.872***	-0.872***	-0.861***
	(0.038)	(0.036)	(0.081)	(0.093)	(0.081)	(0.080)
Ggov	-0.234	11.766***	0.238	0.428	0.238	1.148
	(0.175)	(1.941)	(0.185)	(1.130)	(0.185)	(1.215)
PS		-4.698***		0.484		-0.176
		(0.818)		(0.505)		(0.540)
VA		-8.361***		-1.678**		-1.481**
		(1.052)		(0.688)		(0.735)
GE		-7.992***		1.210		0.535
		(1.529)		(0.783)		(0.839)
RQ		-5.856***		-0.116		-0.441
		(1.140)		(0.640)		(0.689)
CC		-0.326		-0.393		-0.790
		(0.807)		(0.613)		(0.650)
o.RL	-	-		-		1.010
						(0.831)
Constant	32.592***	38.234***	18.068***	15.436***	18.068***	18.040***
	(1.713)	(1.817)	(1.869)	(1.754)	(1.869)	(1.932)
Observations	709	709	709	709	709	709
R-squared	0.468	0.557	0.778	0.786	0.771	0.777
Number of id	41	41	41	41	41	41

Author's compilation. Note: Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Under the specification, our initial hypothesis that the individual-level effects are adequately modeled by a random-effects model is resoundingly rejected based on the Hausman test given that the p-value is significant. Thus, the fixed effects estimates of model are appropriate for further analysis. The coefficient of R-square (0.786) shows that the model is a good fit.

The result based on the FE model reveals that health human capital has a positive significant effect on life expectancy at birth. However, the model depicts a non-linear relationship between the variables. This is realized by the fact that initially, increases in health human capital tend to have a negative impact on life expectancy but the effect becomes positive as the increase in health human capital becomes substantial. This is an indication that enhancing health human capital above a certain threshold will yield positive effect on life expectancy at birth in SSA region. This result concurs with apriori expectations and meshes with the view point of other empirical works such as: Nketiah-Amponsah (2019) Adegoke et al. (2022) and Onofrei et al (2022), Uddin et al (2023) and Anwar et al. 2023.

Also, the results reveal a positive significant relationship between access to water, GDP per capita, institutional quality and degree of urbanization with life expectancy at birth in SSA region. This ties with apriori expectations and past empirical works such as those of Ponku (2019), Rahman (2022), Ahmad et al. (2023). In line with apriori expectations and previous empirical works, the prevalence of HIV/AIDS has negative and significant effect on life expectancy at birth. The high coefficient of HIV (-0.872) suggests that a 1% increase in HIV prevalence rate will lead to 0.872% drop in life expectancy at birth in SSA region.

The result also indicates that increase in carbon emission will lead to increase in life expectancy at birth. This result is not in line with apriori expectations and sounds counter intuitive but this result aligns with the work of Mahalik et al. (2022) who found out that increase in carbon emissions seem to improve life expectancy in developing countries. This result obtained for SSA countries may be explained by the fact that increase carbon emission may be due to increase in production activity, and increase in production implies growth which has a positive effect on wellbeing and life expectancy at birth.

5. Conclusions

The main aim of this study was to investigate the effect of health human capital on life expectancy at birth in SSA. The dependent variable employed in this study is life expectancy and the independent variable, health human capital proxied by health care expenditure per capita. Other control variables included in the study include access to water, GDP per capital, degree of urbanization, HIV prevalence, inflation and institutional quality index composed from all the six governance indicators using the principal component analysis. Data is collected for 42 SSA countries for 21years from the World Bank Development indicators. Given that the study made use of panel data, a series of diagnostic tests such as the test for cross sectional dependence which indicated the use of second generation unit root test on the data. The pooled OLS, Fixed effect model are used to further test the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables.

Our findings revealed a significant relationship between health human capital and life expectancy at birth. Health human capital and Life expectancy indicated a non-linear relationship. That is, health human capital impact life expectancy at birth in SSA region in a quadratic manner. This is seen in the fact that at lower levels of health expenditure, the effect on life expectancy is negative but becomes positive at higher levels of health human capital. This is an indication that enhancing health human capital above a certain threshold will yield positive effects on life expectancy at birth in SSA region.

The results further showed a positive significant correlation between income, access to water, degree of urbanization and life expectancy at birth while HIV/AIDS showed a negative significant relationship with life expectancy at birth. This is because the high rate of HIV prevalence in the SSA region increases mortality rate which has a direct effect on life expectancy at birth. Institutional quality on its part portrays a positive significant relationship with life expectancy at birth. This shows that the quality of institutions in SSA regions is poor and needs to be improved upon to enhance life expectancy at birth.

Based on these findings, the first policy recommendation will be that government of SSA countries should make more efforts towards investing substantially in health human capital through various channels which can enhance health and living standard leading to prolonged life span. Also, the fight against HIV/AIDS should be given more attention in order to reduce mortality rate caused by HIV-related deaths. More sensitization on HIV prevention measures and the consumption of antiretrovirals should be done in order to reduce the rate of infection and mortality, respectively.

There is clear evidence that the quality of institutions in the SSA region has positive net effect on life expectancy. Therefore, the quality of institutions needs to be improved upon in order to improve life expectancy and make expenditure on health human capital effective. It is therefore mandatory on the government of each SSA country to strengthen governance in their countries by improving upon the quality of institutions. A general view on all the governance indicators revealed that most of them do not affect life expectancy at birth but some of them have positive value such as political stability and Government effectiveness which shows that buttressing them will lead to improved life expectancy at birth.

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